

Factors Related to Working Behavior

Charawee Butbumrung

Abstract—This paper aimed to study the factors that relate to working behavior of employees at Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province. A questionnaire was utilized as the tool in collecting information. Descriptive statistics included frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Independent- sample t- test, analysis of variance and Pearson Correlation were also used. The findings of this research revealed that the majority of the respondents were female, between 25- 35 years old, married, with a Bachelor degree. The average monthly salary of respondents was between 8,001- 12,000 Baht, and having about 4-7 years of working experience. Regarding the overall working motivation factors, the findings showed that interrelationship, respect, and acceptance were ranked as highly important factors, whereas motivation, remunerations & welfare, career growth, and working conditions were ranked as moderately important factors. Also, overall working behavior was ranked as high.

The hypotheses testing revealed that different genders had a different working behavior and had a different way of working as a team, which was significant at the 0.05 confidence level. Moreover, there was a difference among employees with different monthly salary in working behavior, problem- solving and decision making, which all were significant at the 0.05 confidence level. Employees with different years of working experience were found to have work working behavior both individual and as a team at the statistical significance level of 0.01 and 0.05. The result of testing the relationship between motivation in overall working revealed that interrelationship, respect and acceptance from others, career growth, and working conditions related to working behavior at a moderate level, while motivation in performing duties and remunerations and welfares related to working behavior towards the same direction at a low level, with a statistical significance of 0.01.

Keywords—Employees of Pakkred Municipality, Factors, Nonthaburi Province, Working Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

A factor crucial for an organization's development and growth especially during period of economic recession is to manage the limited resources which include Man, Money, Material, and Method (4Ms) [1]. In order to manage these limited resources properly, an organization requires high quality human resources. Thus, human resources are essential in driving all operations of an organization towards goal achievement with effectiveness and efficiency.

Individuals in any organization are often diverse in terms of minds and behavior. These differences include needs, motivations, personalities, and working behavior. The majority of employees work to make a living and many times are faced with internal competition in term working quality, working hours, and working to please the boss. This situation

can lead to a lack of caring within the organization, because of mental and physical stress caused by the internal factors and environmental factors as well as personal imbalance (Baron and Greenberg, 1990, p. 226) [2].

During recent years, Pakkred Municipality has faced rapid change and fast pace of development in technology and human resources which has resulted in many mandatory changes within the organization particularly with its human resources. The employees have had changes in their working behavior during the last 1-2 years, for instance, working under rigid rules and regulations, different ways of decision making and as a team, frequent absence and tardiness, and late clock-in. These changes and problems have had negative consequences in organizational harmony and team work. The employees started to lose their dedicated working behavior, loyalty, sense of strong teamwork, and full participation. Furthermore, the organization is facing intense internal competition which has created more conflicts within the organization resulting in poor quality of services (Division of Technical Services and Planning, Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province, as of 31 March, 2011).

The management of Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province has been aware of this negative situation and has realized the importance of fair rules, disciplines, teamwork, enthusiasm and dedication in work, loyalty, corporate with organizational and goal-oriented working styles. In order to achieve these values, employees in the management level must be able to understand the true value of knowledge, capability, and personalities of each subordinate and colleague since this understanding can assist in the integration of the individual objective and the organizational objective. This integration will contribute to the harmony and the cooperation and finally be able to achieve the mission. Moreover, it is vital that with limited human resources, an organization must get a large amount of work done by way of employee dedication. This means all the employees to working towards the same predetermined goal, under the same rules and strict disciplines. By this way, employees will have fulfilled their proper working behavior, and maintain loyalty and commitment.

From the above information, the researcher was therefore interested in investigating factors related to working behavior. The findings should be useful for the management in terms of understanding working behavior and behavioral problems of employees. Also, it is important for the management level to understand the vitality of acquiring new motivation techniques to encourage employees to enhance their performance and productivity and specifically for high level management to design policy.

Dr. Charawee Butbumrungis with the Faculty of Management Science, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, 10300 Thailand.(Corresponding author phone: 662 160 1490; fax: 662 160 1491; e-mail: charawee110@gmail.com).

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Objectives

1. To compare working behavior of the employees at Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province, by demographic factors.
2. To study relationship between working motivation and working behavior of the employees at Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province.

Research Hypotheses

Based on literature survey the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. Do the demographic factors of gender, age, marital status, educational level, monthly salary, and years of work relate to different working behavior for the employees Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province?
2. Does working motivation have a relation with working behaviour for the employees of Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province.

Conceptual Framework

From the literature review, the researcher established the conceptual framework and developed a questionnaire for data collection. The theory of working behavior factors suggested by Porter and Bigley (2004) was applied to and used in creating a conceptualizing the research framework [3]. The independent variable of working behavior, illustrated in Fig. 1, was categorized into 3 groups: rules and disciplines, problem-solving & decision making, and teamwork. From the dependent variables of motivation, the researcher applied the Two-Factor Theory of Herzberg (1959) into the context of this study [4]. In this study, the motivations were categorized into 5 groups: interrelationship, respect & acceptance, remunerations & welfare, career growth, and working condition.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

The population used in this research was 1,083 employees who were working at Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province (the data as of 1 March, 2011). A total of 285 employees who were working at Pakkred Municipality,

Nonthaburi Province were chosen to be included in sample group.

Two stages were conducted to get the 285 respondents.
 Stage one: utilize the Stratified Random Sampling

TABLE I
 SAMPLE SIZE

Number	Division	Proportional Calculation	Sample Size
1	Office of Municipal Clerk	168 (285/1083)	44
2	Division of Technical Services and Planning	31 (285/1083)	8
3	Bureau of Finance	122 (285/1083)	32
4	Internal Audit Unit	3 (285/1083)	1
5	Bureau of Public Works	217 (285/1083)	57
6	Division of Public Health and Environment	411 (285/1083)	109
7	Division of Education	108 (285/1083)	28
8	Division of Social Welfare	23 (285/1083)	6
Total		1,083	285

Stage two: Utilize Simple Random Sampling by distributing the questionnaire to the employees working at Pakkred Municipality according to a predetermined number of eight divisions. In each division, the researcher drew the number in random and then asked the employee to fill out the questionnaire

III. FINDINGS

The study found that the majority of the employees working at Pakkred Municipality, Nonthaburi Province were female, aged between 25- 35 years old, followed by those who were between 36- 45 years old. Most were married. The majority of the respondents had a Bachelor degree followed by those who had High Vocational Certificate. Regarding the salary per month, the majority of the respondents had a salary between 8,001 - 12,000 Baht, followed by 12,001- 16,000 Baht. Most of them had been working there for 4-7 years, followed by the respondents who were working for over 11 years. Regarding the overall working motivation, the study showed that interrelationship and respect and acceptance were ranked highly as important factors, whereas motivation in performing duties, remunerations and welfares, career growth, and working conditions was ranked as moderate important factors. Additionally, overall working behavior was ranked high, including working under rules & regulations, decision making and working as a team.

The results of hypotheses testing unveiled a difference in working behavior and working as a team, at the 0.05 confidence level between genders. Moreover, there was a difference among the employees with different levels of monthly salary; the difference was manifested in working behavior, problem-solving, and decision making, at the 0.05 confidence level. Employees with different years of work were found having difference in working behavior and working as a team at the statistical significance level of 0.01 and 0.05. The result of testing the relations between motivation in overall working behavior revealed that interrelationship, respect & acceptance, career growth, and working conditions related with working behavior towards the same direction at a

moderate level, while motivation in performing duties and remunerations & welfares showed a relation with working behavior towards the same direction at a low level, with a statistical significance of 0.01.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Male and female employees had a difference in working behavior in terms of working as a team at a significant level of 0.05. This suggests that male and female employees had differences ideas in team work, performance improvement, acceptance & respect, different opinions, and suggestion of colleagues. This result concurred with the study by Jularuk Laphaphanwisut (2007), "Factors Influencing Working Behaviour of Bank Officers: Case Study of Bangkok Bank Head Office", which revealed that there was a difference between male and female officers working at Bangkok Bank Head Office in regards to working behavior at a significant level of 0.05 [5].
2. The employees with different salary level had different working behavior in the aspects of problem-solving and decision making, at a significant level of 0.05. A Least Significant Difference (LSD) post hoc test was utilized to detect which of the specific groups differ in mean difference significance. The test found that the employees with the monthly salary between 8,001- 12,000 Baht have less problem-solving and decision making, than those who have the monthly salary over 16,001 Baht. This finding agrees with the equity theory of Supanee Saritwanich (2009), which attempts to explain that employees seek to maintain equity between the inputs that they bring to a job and the outcomes that they receive against the perceived inputs and outcomes of others [6]. Overpayment is accepted by employees and leads to behavior which can appear in many forms such as putting more efforts into works or working harder.
3. The employees with different years of work showed a difference in team work behavior at a significance of 0.01 and 0.05. The LSD post hoc test result revealed that the employees with 4-7 and 8- 11 years of work have higher level of team work behavior than those who have worked for over 11 years. This concurs with the study of Thunrada Jitsuraphon (2010) about motivation, stresses and working behavior of employees of insurance companies in Bangkok, which reported that different personal factors such as years of works had an effect on different working behavior at a significance level of 0.05 [7].
4. Motivations in overall working had a relation with working behavior. These motivations included remunerations & welfares, respect & acceptance, career growth, working conditions, and relationship between management level or leaders and subordinates. Absence of these motivations can decrease quality of job performance for individuals and organizations as a whole. On the other hand, if employees are encouraged in working by using effective motivations, they will be able

to work with higher effectiveness. This is similar to the work of Nucharin Lekkhae (2007), "Correlation Factors of Working Behaviour of the Staffs of the Institute for the Promotion of Teaching Science and Technology (IPST)", which found that overall working motivations had a correlation with working behaviour of IPST staffs towards the same direction at a very low level [8]. Besides, this study agrees with the study of Jularuk Laphaphanwisut (2007), "Factors Influencing Working Behavior of Bank Officers: Case Study of Bangkok Bank Head Office, Silom", which found that motivations related to finance, welfare and career growth opportunities were correlated with working behaviour at a significant of 0.05 [9]. Additionally, the study was well supported by the previous study by Thunrada Jitsuraphon (2010) about motivation, stresses and working behavior of employees of insurance companies in Bangkok. This study explained that motivations had correlations with employees' working behaviour in terms of working under rules and regulations, problem- solving and decision making, and working as a team, towards the same direction at a moderate level at a significance level of 0.05 [10].

V. RECOMMENDATION

1. Organizations should take into account motivation management in order to enhance employees' output. The findings suggest the relations between motivations and working behavior and explained that different employees have different levels of working motivations depending on personal factors, duties and job descriptions, including working environments. Employees with low motivation will perform their duties poorer than those who have high motivation. Thus, management should incorporate the five motivations which are interrelationship, respect & acceptance, remunerations & welfare, career growth, and working condition, in crafting strategies to enhance human resources. In this way, employees will be motivated to have a sense of contribution to organizational success and work towards higher productivity.
2. There should a promotion of relationships between colleagues, subordinates and management. This can be in a form of activities that can increase more effective coordination, and unity. This is to sustain and improve the value of helping and human relations at work. Furthermore, subordinates' success in work will be determined by how well their commanders show their advocate for them.
3. Organizations should set up performance management strategies that cover issues of working capability, work challenges, implementation of knowledge in other areas of work. These contribute to initiates of building teams and unity. In addition, rewarding can be a useful technique in motivating and providing opportunity to employees to develop and improve their performance and competency. As a result, employees will have pride with

their duties and responsibilities, which ultimately moves an organization to its goal.

4. Working condition is a factor in relation with employees' working behavior. Hence, good working environments should be fostered, for instance have a system of good air flow in the workplace, enough resting places for employees during their break. A good workplace environment indirectly helps boost working effectiveness.
5. Working motivation in the aspect of remunerations & welfare has a relation with employees' working behaviour at a low level. Therefore, management should take into account how to increase working motivation of employees through appropriate welfare policy, especially today's higher living cost but income remaining the same. Other ways include the balance between amounts of work and salary, increasing allowances and overtime payment, which can change employees' behavior in a positive way.

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